

PLEDGE

Politics of Grievance and Democratic Governance

Europe and the War in Ukraine: *Susceptibility to Russian Misinformation and Declared Support for Ukraine Across 10 European Countries* March, 2026

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Executive Summary

In 2022, Russia escalated its military aggression against Ukraine by launching a full-scale invasion. This escalation reshaped political agendas and priorities across Europe and intensified the information war. This report summarizes attitudes toward humanitarian support for Ukraine and vulnerability to Russian disinformation in 10 European countries: Belgium, Germany, Spain, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Poland, Sweden, Turkey and the United Kingdom. The findings are based on the analysis of survey data collected in these countries in 2025. The dataset includes responses from more than 20,000 participants across the ten countries.

Introduction

Russia's full-scale aggression toward Ukraine in 2022 had a significant impact on the European political landscape – once again, war has become a close-to-home phenomenon, especially for the countries of Northern and Central Europe. Alongside conventional combat, Russia is also conducting “informational warfare” (Sohl, 2022). In the *Handbook of Russian Information Warfare*, Keir Giles described Russian strategy as “supplying polluted information”.¹ Much of this activity focuses on disinformation in new media², influencing voters and politicians – often with the use of AI technologies (Hunter et al., 2024). In the best-case scenario for Russia, favourable narratives find their way into the policy chain, where they slowly become official state narratives. In a less favorable scenario for Russia – where disinformation only shapes public opinion – the strategy can still be considered effective because it helps create an environment supporting the aggressor. Ultimately, such interference reaffirms the perceived moral and military superiority of the Russian regime, damages Ukraine's image, strengthens groups and political parties hostile to Ukraine, weakens the support it receives, and ultimately makes a Russian victory more likely.

Higher effectiveness of this doctrine in new media stems from higher levels of anonymity and bottom-up direction of community building that occurs without significant moderation. At the same time, social media are becoming increasingly popular and discussions regarding internet control arise in the European Union. In recent years, the EU has strengthened its approach towards misinformation through a combination of platform regulation and anti-

¹ Giles, K. (2016, November). *Handbook of Russian Information Warfare* (Fellowship Monograph No. 9), p. 22. Retrieved February 3, 2026, from NATO Defense College. <https://www.ndc.nato.int/download/handbook-of-russian-information-warfare-by-keir-giles/>

² New media, sometimes referred to as Web 2.0, refers to media that is highly interactive and created by users. The most popular examples of such media are social media and blogs (See: Lister, M., Dovey, J., Giddings, S., Grant, I., & Kelly, K. (2008). *New Media: A Critical Introduction* (2nd ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203884829>)

disinformation initiatives and cybersecurity frameworks, such as the Digital Services Act³, a strengthened Code of Practice on Disinformation⁴ and NIS2⁵.

Considering the links between Russian disinformation, digital media and public attitudes towards Ukraine in Europe, this report aims to provide knowledge about current attitudes in 10 European countries. The data used in the report comes from a study conducted as part of the Horizon Europe project: “Politics of Grievance and Democratic Governance”.

Humanitarian Aid to Ukraine as Political Priority

As part of our research, we asked respondents about various political priorities, including the extent to which humanitarian aid to Ukraine should be a priority for their government. Across the 10 countries, confronting the humanitarian consequences of the war in Ukraine is usually given some political priority, but not equally everywhere. As for the average results (Table X), the matter of humanitarian aid for Ukraine is the highest political priority for citizens of Northern European countries – Sweden (M = 5.65) and Finland (M = 5.63). In these countries, nearly 8 in 10 respondents rated humanitarian support for Ukraine as important and only 1 in 10 respondents considered humanitarian aid unimportant (Figure X).

In contrast, the lowest average ratings were in Poland (M = 4.39), Hungary (M = 4.57), Greece (M = 4.61), and Germany (M = 4.79). In Poland, roughly half of the respondents considered humanitarian aid for Ukraine an important political priority, while about three in ten rated it as not important. A similar pattern appears in Hungary and Greece, where approximately 25% of respondents consider this issue as not important and around 55% treat it as a priority. Importantly, even the lowest country mean remains above the midpoint of the scale, suggesting that humanitarian consequences are, on average, viewed as at least moderately important across all countries.

³ European Commission. (2025, December 15). *The Digital Services Act*. Retrieved February 3, 2026, from <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/digital-services-act>

⁴ European Commission. (n.d.). *A strengthened EU Code of Practice on disinformation*. Retrieved February 3, 2026, from https://commission.europa.eu/topics/countering-information-manipulation/strengthened-eu-code-practice-disinformation_en

⁵ European Commission. (2026, January 2). *NIS2 Directive: securing network and information systems*. Retrieved February 3, 2026, from <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/nis2-directive>

How important is it to you that your country supports confronting the humanitarian consequences of the war in Ukraine?

Scale ranged from 1 (not at all important) to 7 (very important).

Map legend:

< 4.4
 4.4-4.6
 4.6-4.7
 4.7-4.9
 4.9-5.2
 5.2-5.3
 5.3-5.5
 5.5-5.7
 ≥ 5.7

Source: PLEDGE: Politics of Grievance and Democratic Governance • Created with Datawrapper

Figure 1. Mapping humanitarian support for Ukraine as Political Priority (by country).

Figure 2. Humanitarian support for Ukraine as Political Priority (by country).

The data indicate that public opinion across Europe regarding the importance of continuing humanitarian aid to Ukraine varies between countries. These differences should be interpreted in light of several contextual factors. First, it is important to consider the timing of the survey, which was conducted in 2025. By that point, processes of war normalization and signs of war fatigue had already begun to emerge in many European societies. As prolonged conflicts tend to lose salience in public debate, sustained solidarity may gradually weaken. Second, varying levels of support may also be connected to the circulation of specific Russia-narratives that seek to undermine public backing for Ukraine. Among these are claims that Ukraine cannot win the war, that Ukrainians receive unjustified privileges in host countries, or that Ukraine is a fundamentally corrupt state undeserving of continued assistance. Such narratives may contribute to skepticism regarding further aid and reduce the perceived legitimacy of sustained support. Insights from qualitative interviews conducted within the Horizon Europe PLEDGE further suggest that the salience of Ukraine as a political issue has declined in national media environments. Several respondents noted that Ukraine is no longer a dominant topic in the news, as media attention has shifted to other crises and domestic political debates. This decline in media visibility may also play a role in shaping public attitudes, as reduced coverage can weaken emotional engagement and diminish the perceived urgency of continued humanitarian assistance.

Susceptibility towards Russian Misinformation

Based on knowledge of Russian information warfare doctrine, it is possible to predict which narratives may be promoted in European countries to Russia's advantage. In order to assess susceptibility to Russian disinformation, we asked respondents to which extent they agree with the following statements: (1) “We should not provoke Russia by supporting Ukraine”; (2) “Our government should keep us out from the Russian-Ukrainian war”; (3) “In fact, the war in Ukraine is a consequence of NATO actions”. Because selected statements are permissive towards Russia's actions and reframe the situation by blaming NATO or Ukraine for the aggression, the greater approval indicates higher susceptibility to Russian misinformation.

Figure 3. Percentage shares of “agree” and “disagree” answers to the statement: “Our government should keep us out from the Russian-Ukrainian war”.

Across the 10 countries, all of the statements are highly endorsed by respondents from Hungary, Greece and Turkey. Nearly 8 in 10 respondents from Turkey and Greece alongside 7 in 10 respondents from Hungary agree with the statement that their government should keep them out of the Russian-Ukrainian war. Moreover, every second respondent in Greece and Turkey considers Russian aggression as a result of NATO actions and every second respondent in Greece and Hungary thinks that government help towards Ukraine provokes Russia.

Figure 4. Percentage shares of “agree” and “disagree” answers to the statement: “We should not provoke Russia by supporting Ukraine”.

On the other hand, Finland and Sweden show consistently low susceptibility towards Russian information. Only around 2 in 10 respondents from Sweden agree with statements regarding involvement in war, victim-blaming NATO and passiveness towards Russia’s actions. In Finland, 1 in 10 respondents agree with the statements claiming war in Ukraine as a result of

Figure 5. Percentage shares of “agree” and “disagree” answers to the statement: “The war in Ukraine is a consequence of NATO actions”.

NATO actions and helping Ukraine as an act of provocation. Poland also ranked relatively low in terms of agreement with Russian disinformation statements – only 1 in 10 respondents from Poland consider the war as a fault of NATO and every 2 in 10 claim that supporting Ukraine is unwanted as it could provoke Russia.

Relationships between susceptibility to Russian misinformation, social media use and conspiracy mentality

In addition to examining overall levels of belief in misinformation, we explored which factors might be associated with a higher susceptibility to Russian misinformation. We focused on two factors. The first was whether people primarily rely on social media for political news rather than traditional media, online news outlets, or a mix of sources. The second was a conspiracy mentality, namely, a general tendency to believe that powerful groups secretly manipulate important events behind the scenes. As illustrated in Table X, both factors were positively linked to misinformation susceptibility in most of the countries we studied. In particular, conspiracy mentality emerged as a factor most consistently related to the susceptibility to Russian misinformation. People who are more inclined toward conspiratorial thinking were also more receptive to pro-Russian narratives about the war. Relying on social media as a primary news source was also associated with higher susceptibility, though the relationship was weaker than that observed for conspiracy mentality. These patterns suggest that vulnerability to misinformation reflects the sources people turn to for news as well as the broader interpretive lens through which they view political events.

Hungary and Turkey, however, stand out as the most notable exceptions. In these two countries, associations are notably weaker, and in the case of social media usage, essentially absent. This difference may reflect how misinformation circulates in these societies. In countries where pro-Russian narratives are relatively marginal, encountering them requires specific conditions, such as spending time on social media platforms where such content is prevalent or having a predisposition toward conspiratorial explanations. In Hungary and Turkey, where these narratives appear to have a broader reach in mainstream discourse, the population is already more prone to them. In such contexts, relying on social media for news may matter less because misinformation is not confined to online spaces, but rather, it is part of the wider environment that citizens encounter regardless of their media habits.

Insights from qualitative interviews conducted within the Horizon Europe PLEDGE project may help to explain in greater detail the pathways through which disinformation circulates, as many respondents pointed to overlapping media sources, political rhetoric of certain parties, and everyday conversations as mutually reinforcing channels of narrative diffusion. Respondents reported being exposed to some of these narratives not only through social media but also in everyday conversations with colleagues, family members, and other

personal contacts. Such narratives circulate informally through interpersonal communication, becoming part of routine social interaction. Moreover, even when mainstream news coverage does not itself contain explicit disinformation, the comment sections accompanying news articles may serve as important spaces for exposure to Russian-propagated narratives. Some respondents also indicated that certain political parties may function as important channels for the dissemination of Russian-propagated narratives.

Relationships of social media usage and conspiracy mentality with susceptibility to Russian misinformation

Country	Social media usage and susceptibility to Russian misinformation	Conspiracy mentality and susceptibility to Russian misinformation
Belgium	0.13***	0.39***
Germany	0.21***	0.61***
Spain	0.17***	0.23***
Finland	0.20***	0.43***
Greece	0.11***	0.40***
Hungary	-0.04	0.08**
Poland	0.11***	0.42***
Sweden	0.30***	0.39***
Turkey	0.01	0.17***
United Kingdom	0.19***	0.38***

Correlation strength

Weak Strong

Table 1. Susceptibility to Russian misinformation in relation to Social media usage and Conspiracy mentality

Note. ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$. Asterisks indicate statistical significance, meaning that the more asterisks, the more confident we can be that the relationship is genuine and not due to chance. Values without asterisks indicate that there is no sufficient evidence to rule out the possibility that the relationship is equal to zero and therefore non-existent.

This influence can be observed in both online and offline political communication, including campaign messaging, public speeches, and party-affiliated media content. In particular, right-

wing parties were frequently mentioned as actors who reproduce or amplify frames aligned with pro-Russian positions.

Taken together, these findings suggest that susceptibility to Russian misinformation cannot be reduced to one particular factor or media choice, rather, it is embedded in hybrid communicative environments where media systems, political views, conspiracy mentality, and interpersonal networks intersect .

Conclusions

The conclusions from comparing ten countries point to one practical implication – the same set of war-related narratives is present across Europe, but patterns of susceptibility vary markedly by country. Treating “European public opinion” as a single whole is therefore misleading. Receptiveness to messages that diffuse Russia’s responsibility and shift blame onto the West is strongly associated with whether audiences have a stable tendency to interpret politics through a conspiratorial lens. At the same time, the data suggest that in many countries susceptibility to such narratives is linked to relying on social media as the main source of political news. In contrast, in others – notably Hungary and Turkey – this link is weak or absent, suggesting that these frames may have a broader reach beyond social media. Insights from qualitative interviews suggest that exposure to pro-Russian narratives also occurs through other channels, including political rhetoric, interpersonal conversations, and comment sections accompanying mainstream news, which interact with online media to reinforce credibility and normalize certain interpretations of the war. For journalists, policy-makers, and activists fighting disinformation, this means a segmented approach to communication is needed. Efforts should be tailored to national contexts, recognizing that susceptibility is shaped by both structural factors, such as media ecosystems and dominant political narratives, and individual interpretive lenses. In each case, attention should be paid not only to what people think about the war, but also to what makes certain narratives seem credible to them.

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